

colour of the solution corresponding to inflexion at 6.7 ml was cherry red which was due to the formation of trivalent manganese in the solution and was confirmed by spectrophotometric measurements which showed maximum absorption at 500 nm.

The stoichiometry observed was

TABLE I—POTENTIOMETRIC DATA OF REDUCTION OF Br(V) BY Mn(II)

(Cell: 10 ml BrO_3^- , Reductant M/10 manganous sulphate)

Medium 3N H_2SO_4 , Temp. $25^\circ \pm 0.05^\circ$

Storage time	Position of inflexion in ml	Nature of inflexion
1.5 hr	1.8	Very sharp
	6.7	
3 hrs	1.8	Sharp
	3.4	
	6.7	
24 hrs	1.8	Very sharp
	3.4	
	6.8	

The observation is in good agreement with the work of Thompson¹⁰.

In case of reduction of Br(V) with Ce(III) only one inflexion was obtained at 8.5 ml after 1 hr storage of the reaction mixture at room temperature which corresponds to 5th electron reduction stage of Br(V). Even after 24 and 48 hrs storage of the reaction mixture the only inflexion obtained at 8.5 ml which is suggestive of the formation of bromine, also supports the 5th electron reduction stage of Br(V).

Tris (1, 10-phenanthroline) iron(II) and tris (2,2'-dipyridyl) ruthenium(II) act as reductants. The formal reduction potential³ of $\text{Fe(phen)}_3^{2+} - \text{Fe(phen)}_3^{3+}$ couple is 1.1 v and for $\text{Ru(dipy)}_3^{2+} - \text{Ru(dipy)}_3^{3+}$ is 1.25 v. Reaction of Br(V) with $[\text{Fe(phen)}_3]^{2+}$ and $[\text{Ru(dipy)}_3]^{2+}$ showed consumption of 10.2 and 10.4 ml of the reductants respectively which suggests 6th electron reduction stage of Br(V) in both the cases. Presence of Br^- at those stages were confirmed.

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Base Adducts of Bis-(Chloro Acetyl-Acetonato)-Zinc(II) with Nitrogen Donors

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METAL chelates of beta-diketones and related compounds which involve keto-enol tautomerism have invoked lot of interest in recent years. Attempts have been made for the adduct formation of metal beta-diketonates with heterocyclic amines and a number of pentacoordinated adducts of zinc(II) and copper(II) beta-diketonates with nitrogen donors have been reported¹⁻⁷. Stability of acetyl acetonates has been partly explained on the basis of benzenoid resonance⁸ and reactions characteristic of aromatic systems have been carried out⁹⁻¹¹ on metal acetyl acetonates to provide further evidence regarding aromaticity. It was thought worthwhile to study the adduct formations of gamma-substituted beta-diketonates and as a part of this investigation adducts of bis-(nitroacetyl-acetonato) copper(II) have been reported^{12,13}. This communication reports four pentacoordinated adducts of bis-(chloroacetylacetonato)-zinc(II) with quinoline, isoquinoline, gamma-picoline and quinaldine.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Bis-(chloroacetylacetonato) zinc(II) was prepared by reacting a methanolic solution of the metal chelate with dry chlorine gas and by cooling the reaction mixture in an ice bath. The white compound separated was filtered, washed with methanol, followed by ether and dried in vacuum. Analysis of the compound indicated the composi-

TABLE I—ANALYSIS, M.P., CONDUCTANCE AND IR SPECTRAL DATA

Compounds	M.P. °C.	Conduc- tance (mhos cm ²)	% Zinc		% Chlorine		% Nitrogen		$\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$	$\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$	$\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$
			Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.				
[Zn(Cl-AcAc) ₂ H ₂ O]	138	—	20.94	21.13	22.28	22.62	—	—	1600	1520	430	—
[Zn(Cl-AcAc) ₂ γ -pic]	143	8.5	16.73	17.00	18.51	18.99	3.55	3.64	1630	1595	420	330
[Zn(Cl-AcAc) ₂ Q]	220	8.8	16.18	15.55	16.25	16.65	3.23	3.33	1620	1530	425	320
[Zn(Cl-AcAc) ₂ I.Q.]	175	9.2	15.24	15.55	16.31	16.65	3.21	3.33	1625	1540	420	320
[Zn(Cl-AcAc) ₂ Quin.]	122	9.8	14.81	15.05	15.86	16.11	3.13	3.22	1630	1590	425	325

Cl.AcAc=chloro acetyl acetate ; γ -pic=4-methyl pyridine ; Q=quinoline ; I.Q.=isoguinoline ; Quin=quinaldine.

tion Zn(Cl-AC.AC)₂H₂O. IR spectra provided evidence for the formation of the chelate. Adducts were prepared by refluxing ethanolic solution of the chelate with nitrogen ligands in 1 : 2 ratio for three hours. On cooling overnight, crystalline compounds separated out which were filtered, washed with ethanol followed by ether and dried in vacuum.

Metal was estimated by EDTA titration method, halogen by gravimetric method and nitrogen by microanalytical method. Conductance was measured in M/1000 acetone solution of the complexes using Toshniwal conductivity bridge. IR spectra were recorded on KBr phase using Perkin-Elmer-621 spectrophotometer. All the relevant analytical, conductance and spectral data are given in Table I.

Results and Discussion

Complexes reported in the present investigation have a general formula [Zn(Cl-AcAc)₂L], where L is the nitrogen donor ligands. These are white crystalline solids, have low melting points and are fairly soluble in acetone in which medium they behave as non-electrolytes, the Λ_M values being in the range of 8-10 mhos. cm².

Infrared spectra of the chelate, chloroacetylacetate and the base adducts have been studied. It is seen that the C=C and C=O stretching frequencies of the chelates shift to lower frequency and the bands due to C-H stretching and bending vibrations disappear on chlorination. The extent of decrease in the frequency is more in case of $\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$. Disappearance of bands due to $\nu(\text{C}-\text{H})$ at 3000 cm⁻¹ and $\delta(\text{C}-\text{H})$ around 1200 cm⁻¹ and appearance of a new band around 800 cm⁻¹ attributable to $\nu(\text{C}-\text{Cl})$ provides evidence for the chloroacetylacetate. However, the coordinated water band due to $\nu(\text{O}-\text{H})$ is observed as a broad hump at 3450 cm⁻¹ both in the chelate and the chloroanalogue. In the base adducts most of the absorption bands due to free nitrogen ligands are shifted indicating bonding of the nitrogen donor ligands, the information being obtained by the finger print technique as the

assignment of these bands is complicated. Concrete evidence for bonding of the ligands is obtained from the shift of $\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$ and $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ to higher frequency regions in the base adducts and the disappearance of the water band present in the chloroacetylacetate. This has been further substantiated by observation of $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$ and $\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$ ~430 and ~320 cm⁻¹ respectively in the far infrared spectra of the adducts.

Hence a molecule of the nitrogen ligand has replaced the water molecule in the chloroacetylacetate maintaining pentacoordination. Earlier mono-aquo-(bis-acetylacetate) zinc(II) and its mono base adducts have been found to be monomeric and presumably pentacoordinated, though a few bis-adducts have also been reported by Graddon¹.

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